

What is ORCID?

The Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID) is a persistent identifier that distinguishes you from other researchers, ensuring all your work is correctly attributed.

Why Connect Them?

Connecting your research outputs to your ORCID record ensures that your contributions are visible and attributed, increasing the impact of your work.

What is DataCite?

DataCite supports research organizations worldwide to make their research outputs and activities more discoverable, citable, and connected.

MAKE THE CONNECTION

OPTION 1

ORCID AUTO-UPDATE

The most efficient method for continuously updating your ORCID record.

How it Works

Once enabled, DataCite will automatically add works to your ORCID record whenever your ORCID iD is included as a creator in DataCite DOI metadata.

Steps

1. Click the "Sign In" button on the top right of DataCite Commons and use your ORCID credentials to sign in.
2. Click "Click to Enable" under "ORCID Auto-Update".
3. You will then be prompted to approve DataCite's permission to automatically add works.
4. Going forward, works including your ORCID iD in DataCite metadata will be added to your ORCID record.

OPTION 2

IMPORT WORKS FROM OTHER SERVICES

Ideal for manually adding specific works or reviewing items before adding.

How it Works

Manually select works from **DataCite Commons** and add them to your ORCID record.

Steps

1. Log in to your ORCID account and go to the "Works" section.
2. Click the "Add" button and select "Import works from other services".
3. Scroll down and choose "DataCite" from the list.
4. You will be taken to DataCite Commons. Search for your works using your name or ORCID iD.
5. Click on a work record, then click the "Add to ORCID Record" button to add it to your profile.

DataCite Commons <https://commons.datacite.org/>

A discovery tool where you can search for your research and link it to your ORCID record.